

Figurate Geometry: Order-5 Triangle Labelings

Working paper by Steven H. Cullinane on April 4, 2024

Study of triangle structure as an approach to finding natural mappings from a 25-part array of square cells to a 25-part array of triangular cells.

Some arbitrary symmetric partitions of an order-5 triangular array. The blank center corresponds to a possible future (0,0) label under possible future affine coordinatizations over $GF(5)$.

It seems fairly easy to construct such symmetric partitions, so they may be of some use in the study of Mathieu group actions on 24 elements ... as is the Miracle Octad Generator of R. T. Curtis, in which the corresponding partitions are of a 4x6 rectangular array.

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